

Nitrogen Ligated Complexes with Polyiodide Anion, I_3^-

A. K. MAJUMDAR, B. C. BHATTACHARYYA and ARUN K. MUKHERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-32.

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A few nickel(II) complexes of heterocyclic bases with a polyiodide anion have been isolated. Paramagnetic eight coordinated complex, $NiPy_7(H_2O)I_6$, has been characterised and from which a diamagnetic planar compound $NiPy_4I_6$ has been prepared by thermolysis. Corresponding complexes with quinoline and isoquinoline are paramagnetic and tetrahedral. X-ray powder diffraction data are given in support of the tetrahedral structure.

THE nickel complexes¹⁻⁵ of the types NiL_4X_2 , NiL_2X_2 , $NiLX_2$ (L=monodentate ligand coordinating through nitrogen, X=anion) are mostly octahedral complexes and those with tetrahedral configuration are few and of the octahedral complexes many are anion bridged. The bidentate ligand, ethylenediamine or its N-substituted derivatives, also yield complexes which are anion bridged and are octahedral. The substitution of these anions by more polarisable ones produce planar diamagnetic complexes⁶.

Herein is reported a few nickel complexes of heterocyclic bases with polyiodide anion. The first such compound prepared is of the composition $NiPy_7(H_2O)I_6$, where the coordination number of nickel appears to be eight. This is further confirmed by IR analysis. The infra-red spectra of this compound shows a broad band at 3392 cm^{-1} due to coordinated water. Moreover, near 1600 cm^{-1} there is a band at 1613 cm^{-1} of

medium intensity with two shoulders, at 1598 cm^{-1} and 1622 cm^{-1} . The lowest energy band may be assigned as C=C stretch but those at 1613 and 1622 cm^{-1} are probably the C=N vibration of the pyridine molecules and are appearing at higher wave numbers due to coordination⁷. The complex is fully paramagnetic and stable in the solid state in the cold but is unstable in solution in organic solvents except pyridine from which it can be recrystallised unchanged. On heating for about 12 hr at $80^\circ\text{-}90^\circ$, it gives a new product of the formula $NiPy_4I_6$. This being completely diamagnetic may be suggested to have planar configuration. The brown compound $NiPy_4I_6$ on further heating at 110° for 10 hr loses iodine to form a green paramagnetic complex $NiPy_4I_2$. Thermogravimetric curve (Fig. 1) indicates the presence of another unstable intermediate $NiPy_2I_2$, the isolation of which in the pure state was mentioned previously¹. The trend of decomposition is $NiPy_7(H_2O)I_6 \rightarrow NiPy_4I_6 \rightarrow NiPy_4I_2 \rightarrow NiPy_2I_2 \rightarrow NiI_2 \rightarrow NiO$.

Fig. 1 Thermolysis curves of the complexes A. $Ni(C_5H_5N)_7 H_2OI_6$. B. $Ni(C_5H_7N)_4I_6$. C. $Ni(i-C_5H_7N)_4I_6$

Since the first two compounds are unstable even in organic solvents such as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, etc. their solution spectra could not be measured.

With quinoline (Q) and iso-quinoline (i-Q), complexes of the types NiQ_4I_6 and $N:(i-Q)_4I_6$ have also been isolated. These are paramagnetic and are found to be tetrahedral on comparison of their X-ray powder diffraction pattern with analogous zinc compounds (cf. Table 2). The difference in magnetic moment value and structure between quinoline and isoquinoline complexes, NiQ_4I_6 and $Ni(i-Q)_4I_6$, on the one hand and the pyridine complex $NiPy_4I_6$ on the other may be suggested to be due to distance of approach of the organic molecule. The quinoline and isoquinoline molecules cannot make a closer approach to the central atom. The packing of these molecules may, therefore, be such as to force the structural arrangement to a tetrahedral one in preference to the planar form. All these are stable in the solid state but unstable in solutions of organic solvents mentioned. Table 1 comprises data on colour, magnetic moment and decomposition temperature of the isolated complexes, while in Table 2 are given the powder diffraction data.

TABLE 1—COLOUR, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE OF THE COMPLEXES.

Compound	Colour	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Decomposition t°C
1. $NiPy_7(H_2O)I_6$	Black	2.92	62
2. $NiPy_4I_6$	Brown	Diamagnetic	—
3. NiQ_4I_6	Black	2.37	94
4. $Ni(i-Q)_4I_6$	Brown	2.30	110

Slightly low magnetic moment values of NiQ_4I_6 and $Ni(i-Q)_4I_6$ compared to what is expected of a tetrahedral complex with identical ligands may result from the presence of a low percentage of planar species.

Attempts to prepare the compound of the type $NiPy_7(H_2O)I_6$ with substitution of pyridine by α , β and γ -picolines or lutidines have not been of success because the solid products so obtained invariably decompose during crystallisation.

Experimental

1. $Ni(C_5H_5N)_7(H_2O)I_6(I)$. To a solution of nickel chloride hexahydrate (4.8 g) was added in succession a potassium tri-iodide solution, prepared by dissolving potassium iodide (6.7 g) and iodine (10.2 g) in a minimum quantity of water and pyridine (15 ml), with vigorous stirring, when an oil separated. The watery portion was decanted off and the oil was washed with water several times by decantation. The excess pyridine was then removed by vacuum suction and the oily product was kept in the refrigerator till it solidified. It was then dissolved in minimum amount of pyridine and treated with ether, when beautiful shining black crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with ether and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride [Found : Ni, 4.16 ; N, 6.95 ; C, 30.02 ; H, 2.58 ; I, 54.43. Calcd. Ni, 4.22 ; N, 7.05 ; C, 30.19 ; H, 2.66 ; I, 54.70%].

2. $Ni(C_5H_5N)_4I_6$. (I) was heated at 80°-90° for 12 hr when the compound was formed [Found : Ni, 5.10 ; N, 4.85 ; C, 21.19 ; H, 1.80 ; I, 66.90. Calcd. Ni, 5.17 ; N, 4.92 ; C, 21.13 ; H, 1.76 ; I, 67.00%].

3. $Ni(C_9H_7N)_4I_6$. The method of preparation was the same as followed for (I), except that quinoline, in place of pyridine, was used [Found : Ni, 4.36 ; N, 4.17 ; C, 32.37 ; H, 2.14 ; I, 56.91. Calcd. Ni, 4.39 ; N, 4.19 ; C, 32.33 ; H, 2.09 ; I, 56.99%].

4. $Ni(i-C_9H_7N)_4I_6$. The same procedure as described under 3 was followed with the use of isoquinoline instead of quinoline [Found : Ni, 4.37 ; N, 4.17 ; I, 56.89. Calcd. Ni, 4.39 ; N, 4.19 ; I, 56.99%].

Zn complexes : The zinc complexes of quinoline and isoquinoline with the tri-iodide anion were prepared according to the procedure suggested for the corresponding nickel complexes. The purity of the two complexes were checked by the elemental analysis.

Analysis of Iodide : The weighed amount of the complex was dissolved in 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solution and filtered. The filtrate was collected in

TABLE 2—DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF QUINOLINE AND ISOQUINOLINE COMPOUNDS.

Zn-Q		Ni-Q		Zn-i-Q		Ni-i-Q	
d in Å°	I/I'						
7.68	8	7.66	9	7.66	8	7.65	10
6.70	2	6.68	2(b)	6.67	2(b)	6.67	1(b)
6.40	9	6.41	8	6.41	9	6.39	9
5.32	5	5.33	5	5.32	6	5.31	5
5.19	7	5.18	6	5.19	7	5.19	6
4.13	10	4.13	10	4.13	10	4.13	10
3.82	8	3.83	7	3.82	7	3.85	7
3.70	8	3.71	8	3.70	9	3.70	8
3.52	6	3.52	4(b)	3.52	6	3.52	4
3.44	5(b)	3.44	3	3.44	4	3.44	3(b)
3.35	2(b)	3.36	3(b)	3.35	3(b)	3.33	3(b)
3.22	2	3.23	2(b)	3.22	1(b)	3.22	2(b)
3.14	8	3.16	5	3.14	9	3.13	8(b)
2.81	5	2.80	4(b)	2.81	4	2.81	2(b)

b = broad.

250 ml volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with water. A measured quantity of the solution from the volumetric flask was taken in a beaker and boiled with an excess of sulphur dioxide solution until the solutions became colourless. The excess of sulphur dioxide was boiled off and the iodide was precipitated with dilute silver nitrate solution (0.7N) after acidifying with dilute nitric acid with stirring. Filtered in a weighed gooch crucible, washed with 0.01–0.02 N nitric acid, dried at 130° for 1 hr and weighed.

A Chevenard thermobalance, type 3 of ADAMEL of Paris, was used to record photographically the loss in weight of the heated substance as a function of temperature. Rate of heating was 5°/min.

The magnetic measurements at room temperature were made by the Gouy method, with mercury tetra thiocyanato cobaltate as the standard.

The diffraction patterns were recorded in Philips Pw-1010 crystallographic unit. Guiner camera fitted with quartz crystal mono-chromator was used. Time of exposure was 7.5 hr with CuK α radiation.

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